

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide as a Reagent for the Gravimetric Determination of Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II)

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Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) have been precipitated with benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide as Ni(C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₂)₂ and Co(C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₂)₂·2H₂O at pH 6.5-7.0 and 5.4-7.0 respectively. The complexes were dried at 120° for weighing. The presence of Ag⁺ and TI⁺ do not effect the estimation. As magnesium-EDTA, I⁻, F⁻, citric acid and ascorbic acid do not interfere, using a suitable masking agent from this list separation of the above two metal ions from Cd²⁺, Cu²⁺, Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺, Bi³⁺, Cr³⁺, Al³⁺, Fe³⁺, Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, Zr⁴⁺, VO²⁺, WO₄²⁻ or MoO₄²⁻ is possible. Cobalt has also been separated from nickel by precipitating the former with benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide at pH 8.5 in the presence of thiocyanate. Nickel has been determined with the same reagent after removing thiocyanate. The nickel content of some samples of steel and nickel-ore has also been estimated. The standard deviation has been calculated as ±0.17% and ±0.07% in 40 determinations of nickel and cobalt respectively.

THIO-UREAS¹, thiols^{2,3}, thioacids^{4,5} and their derivatives⁶⁻⁸ and similar sulphur-containing ligands have been widely used for the gravimetric determination of nickel(II), the other class of interesting reagents being dioximes, especially dimethylglyoxime⁹. Cobalt(II) is generally estimated gravimetrically using α -nitroso- β -naphthol¹⁰, though the use of a few nitrogen-containing precipitants like amino-acids¹¹ and oximes¹² or some thio-compounds¹³⁻¹⁵ has been reported. However, the chelates of cobalt with organic ligands often have low thermal stability.

The use of benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide as a gravimetric reagent¹⁶⁻¹⁸ has already been reported. This reagent, though possesses functional groups which form chelates through oxygen has been employed in this investigation for the direct gravimetric determination of nickel(II) and cobalt(II), their separation from one another and from 16 other metal ions.

Experimental

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide: The reagent was prepared following the method due to Weissberger *et al.*¹⁹. A 0.85% solution of the reagent in aqueous ethanol was used.

Nickel(II) solution: A stock solution of nickel sulphate (G.R., E. Merck) in 0.1M hydrochloric acid was prepared and the metal content was determined gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime.

Cobalt(II) solution: The stock solution was prepared by dissolving cobalt(II) nitrate (A.R., B.D.H.) in 0.1M nitric acid. The cobalt content was estimated with α -nitroso- β -naphthol.

Diverse ions: Aqueous solutions of other metal ions were prepared from their chlorides, sulphates or nitrates. Small quantities of any suitable acid were added to prevent hydrolysis in case of heavier metals. For studying the effect of tungstate or molybdate either sodium or ammonium salt was used. The metal content was determined gravimetrically or by titration with disodium ethylenediamine tetraacetate (Na₂EDTA).

Magnesium-EDTA solution: Aqueous solutions of magnesium chloride (0.1M) and Na₂ EDTA (0.1M) were prepared separately and 20 ml of each was mixed before use.

pH meter: A battery-operated bench model Cambridge pH-meter was used.

Procedure for nickel(II): A known quantity of nickel (7-15 mg) solution was diluted to 150 ml, the pH was adjusted to 4.0-4.5 with sodium or ammonium acetate (2%) solution and heated to boiling. The reagent (0.15-0.20 g) solution was added with stirring and the pH was raised to 6.5-7.0 with aqueous ammonia (2M). The solution with the yellowish precipitate formed was left on a hot water-bath for 30 min. The complex was filtered, washed first with hot water and finally with aqueous ethanol (20%). It was dried at 120° before weighing as Ni(C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₂)₂. The conversion factor is 0.0939 and the results are given in Table 1.

Procedure for cobalt(II): The procedure for cobalt(II) was similar to that of nickel(II). But the pH was first adjusted to 3.0-4.0 with sodium acetate (2%) solution before the addition of the reagent and finally it was raised to 5.4-7.0 for the complete precipitation of cobalt. The yellow complex, Co

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(C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₂)₂, 2H₂O was weighed after drying at 120° and for calculations the factor 0.0890 was used. Table 1 also contains the results of the estimation of cobalt.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION AND SEPARATION OF NICKEL AND COBALT

Ni taken mg	Ni found mg	Rel. error, %	Co taken mg,	Co found mg	Rel. error, %
12.50	12.50	nil	—	—	—
	12.52	+0.16	—	—	—
15.00	15.04	+0.26	—	—	—
	14.94	-0.40	—	—	—
7.50	7.50	nil	—	—	—
	7.53	+0.40	—	—	—
—	—	—	13.72	13.70	-0.40
				13.73	+0.07
—	—	—	10.49	10.51	+0.19
				10.49	nil
—	—	—	7.58	7.58	nil
				7.61	+0.39
12.50	12.48	-0.16	10.49	10.52	+0.28
	12.51	+0.08		10.48	-0.09
7.50	7.53	+0.40	13.72	13.75	+0.21
	7.49	-0.13		13.71	-0.07
15.00	14.95	-0.33	7.50	7.53	+0.40
	14.98	-0.13		7.50	nil

Procedure for nickel(II) and cobalt(II) present together: The mixture containing nickel and cobalt was adjusted to pH 3.0-4.0 with sodium acetate (2%) solution and 1 g of ammonium thiocyanate was added. It was heated to 70°, the reagent (0.2 g) solution was added and pH was raised to 8.5 with aqueous ammonia (2M) to precipitate the cobalt complex. It was filtered after digestion for 30 min on a hot water-bath, washed, dried and weighed as described before.

The filtrate with the washings containing nickel was concentrated, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and boiled to decompose thiocyanate. The pH was then raised to 4.0-4.5, further reagent was added and the procedure for nickel described earlier was followed. The results of these separations have also been presented in Table 1.

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions: In the presence of foreign metal ions, two modifications were necessary. First, some suitable masking agent was added before the addition of the reagent and the mixture was boiled for a few minutes. Secondly,

the final pH was adjusted to 7.0-7.5 for the complete precipitation of nickel or cobalt. For both nickel and cobalt, 1 g of citric acid was used to mask Cd²⁺, Cu²⁺, MoO₄²⁻, 1 g KI masked Hg²⁺ and WO₄²⁻, 40 ml of magnesium-EDTA was sufficient for Bi³⁺, Cr³⁺, Al³⁺, Zr⁴⁺ and VO²⁺ and for Fe³⁺ and Mn²⁺ 1 g of ammonium fluoride was used. Citrate and magnesium-EDTA were also used to separate Zn²⁺ and Pb²⁺ respectively from cobalt. Nickel was precipitated in presence of zinc using fluoride and lead was masked with 0.5 g of ascorbic acid. However, no masking agent was required to separate nickel or cobalt from Ag⁺ or Tl⁺. The results of these separations are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Ni²⁺ OR Co²⁺ FROM DIVERSE IONS

Individual experiments: Ni²⁺ taken 12.50 mg or Co²⁺ taken 10.49 mg.

Diverse ion, mg.	Masking agent	For Nickel		For Cobalt	
		Ni ²⁺ found mg	Rel. error %	Co ²⁺ found mg	Rel. error %
Ag ⁺ , 50	—	12.50	nil	10.50	+0.07
		12.50	nil	10.47	-0.19
Tl ⁺ , 50	—	12.48	-0.16	10.53	+0.38
		12.51	+0.08	10.48	-0.09
Cd ²⁺ , 50	a	12.47	-0.24	10.51	+0.19
		12.51	+0.08	10.52	+0.28
Cu ²⁺ , 50	a	12.51	+0.08	10.50	+0.09
		12.48	-0.16	10.49	nil
Hg ²⁺ , 50	b	12.48	-0.16	10.49	nil
		12.50	nil	10.45	-0.38
Pb ²⁺ , 40	e for Ni ²⁺ c for Co ²⁺	12.53	+0.24	10.46	-0.28
		12.49	-0.08	10.48	-0.09
Bi ³⁺ , 50	c	12.45	-0.40	10.52	+0.28
		12.48	-0.16	10.50	+0.09
Cr ³⁺ , 50	c	12.50	nil	10.46	-0.28
		12.53	+0.24	10.48	-0.09
Al ³⁺ , 50	c	12.47	-0.24	10.53	+0.38
		12.49	-0.08	10.51	+0.19
Fe ³⁺ , 70	d	12.44	-0.48	10.53	+0.38
		12.45	-0.40	10.50	+0.09
Mn ²⁺ , 50	d	12.54	+0.48	10.51	+0.19
		12.49	-0.08	10.45	-0.38
Zn ²⁺ , 50	d for Ni ²⁺ a for Co ²⁺	12.50	nil	10.46	-0.28
		12.53	+0.24	10.51	+0.19
Zr ⁴⁺ , 50	c	12.51	+0.08	10.48	-0.09
		12.48	-0.16	10.51	+0.19
VO ²⁺ , 50	c	12.50	nil	10.49	nil
		12.50	nil	10.52	+0.38
WO ₄ ²⁻ , 40	b	12.48	-0.16	10.53	+0.38
		12.51	+0.08	10.47	-0.19
MoO ₄ ²⁻ , 40	a	12.49	-0.08	10.51	+0.19
		12.48	-0.16	10.49	nil

(a) = citric acid; (b) = KI; (c) = Magnesium-EDTA; (d) = NH₄F; (e) = Ascorbic acid.

Procedure for nickel in steel: About 0.1 g of steel was dissolved in hydrochloric-nitric acid mixture and then fumed with sulphuric acid. It was then diluted, filtered and treated with 1 g of sodium sulphite. After boiling off the excess of sulphur dioxide, the pH was adjusted to 4.0–4.5 with ammonium acetate solution, 40 ml of magnesium-EDTA solution was added and nickel was determined following the procedure for nickel given earlier. For the final washing of the nickel complex a hot solution of aqueous alcohol (60%) was used. The results are presented in Table 3.

Procedure for nickel in ore: About 0.5 g of the ore was dissolved in a mixture of hydrochloric and nitric acid and heated to fumes with sulphuric acid. The solution was diluted, filtered and filtrate was preserved. The residue was ignited, treated with hydrofluoric acid and the mass left behind was taken up with dilute sulphuric acid. It was filtered and the filtrate was mixed with the original one. This was then treated with 1 g of sodium sulphite. The excess of sulphur dioxide was boiled off. The pH was adjusted to 3.0–4.0 with sodium acetate solution and 1 g each of ammonium thiocyanate and fluoride were added. Any cobalt present in the ore was precipitated at pH 8.5 as described under the 'procedure for nickel and cobalt present together' and nickel was determined as described already after adding 0.5 g more of fluoride. The results of these estimations have also been given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL IN STEEL AND ORES

Sample	Composition %	Sample taken, mg	Ni found %	Rel. error %
	Cr, 17.5	105.2	9.50	+0.21
Steel	C, 0.10 Ni, 9.48	99.5	9.45	-0.31
	Ni, 1.50	562.5	1.51	+0.66
Ni Ore	Co, 0.015 Fe, major	502.5	1.48	-1.33

Results and Discussion

Properties and composition of the complexes: Both the nickel(II)- and cobalt(II)-bis-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complexes were found to be appreciably soluble in acetone, though practically insoluble in ethanol, tributyl phosphate or chloroform. The pure complexes, dried at 120° were analysed for nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method (using glucose for the reduction of nitro-group) as well as for nickel and cobalt. The complexes were decomposed with acid and subsequently cobalt was estimated as cobalt sulphate while dimethylglyoxime was used for nickel. The experimental results—Ni 9.41, 9.35% (theo. 9.39%), N 8.92, 8.94% (theo. 8.96%) and Co 8.86, 8.96% (theo. 8.90%), N 8.62, 8.84% (theo. 8.47%) were in agreement with the formula assigned, Ni (C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₂)₂ and Co (C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₂)₂·2H₂O respectively.

The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes was measured in a modified electrodynamic microbalance developed by Neogy and Lal²⁰. The data obtained for the nickel (χ_m , 3329×10^{-6} cgs units and μ , 2.87 B.M.) and cobalt (χ_m , 8600×10^{-6} cgs units and μ , 4.60 B.M.) complexes supported the formula assigned to them.

The nickel complex was found to be stable upto 180° while the cobalt complex lost the water molecules around 150° and decomposed completely at 525°.

Effect of pH: The precipitation of the nickel and cobalt complexes commenced at pH 5.0 and 4.5 respectively while the precipitation was complete at pH 6.5–7.0 in case of nickel and at 5.4–7.0 in case of cobalt. However, in the presence of thiocyanate cobalt was quantitatively precipitated only above pH 8.5.

Effect of the concentration of the reagent: The precipitation of nickel or cobalt was carried out at fixed pH values (6.8 for nickel, 5.8 for cobalt) using varied amounts of the reagent, maintaining all other conditions identical. For the complete precipitation the supernatant liquid should be at least 0.02% with respect to the reagent in either case.

Effect of sequestering agents: Reasonable quantities of iodide, magnesium-EDTA, ammonium fluoride, ascorbic acid or citric acid did not hinder the estimation of either nickel or cobalt, though tartrate and sulphosalicylic acid prevented the precipitation of both the metals. Ammonium thiocyanate masked the precipitation of nickel but not that of cobalt. Thus using suitable masking agents for various foreign ions the determination of nickel or cobalt could be rendered very selective and the separation of cobalt from nickel could be effected.

Precision and accuracy: The standard deviation was found to be $\pm 0.17\%$ and $\pm 0.07\%$ for nickel and cobalt respectively in 40 determinations of each.

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